

PRAGMALINGUISTIC APPROACH TO ANECDOTE TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the importance of anecdote translation and pragmalinguistic approaches. Anecdotes represent a unique genre of oral folk art with distinctive characteristics across different languages and cultures. The necessity of applying pragmalinguistic approaches in the accurate and effective translation of anecdotes is emphasized, as anecdotes are often constructed through wordplay, irony, and cultural references. The pragmalinguistic approach analyzes the purpose of a anecdote and how it is received by the audience, taking into account the social and contextual aspects of language.*

Keywords: *anecdotes, pragmalinguistic approach, translation, wordplay, cross-cultural differences, social context, humor, irony, cultural references.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola latifalar tarjimasi va pragmalingvistik yondashuvning ahamiyatini tahlil qiladi. Latifalar xalq og‘zaki ijodining o‘ziga xos janri bo‘lib, turli tillar va madaniyatlarda o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Latifalarni to‘g‘ri va samarali tarjima qilishda pragmalingvistik yondashuvni qo‘llash zarurligi ta’kidlanadi, chunki latifalar ko‘pincha so‘z o‘yinlari, kinoya va madaniy ishoralar orqali tuzilgan bo‘ladi. Pragmalingvistik yondashuv tilning ijtimoiy va kontekstual jihatlarini hisobga olgan holda, latifaning maqsadi va auditoriya tomonidan qanday qabul qilinishini tahlil qiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *latifalar, pragmalingvistik yondashuv, tarjima, til o‘yinlari, madaniyatlararo farqlar, ijtimoiy kontekst, hazil, kinoya, madaniy ishoralar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается перевод анекдотов и значение прагмалигвистического подхода. Анекдоты являются специфическим жанром народного творчества и имеют свои особенности в разных языках и культурах. Подчеркивается необходимость применения прагмалигвистического подхода при правильном и эффективном переводе анекдотов, поскольку они часто строятся через игру слов, иронию и культурные намеки. Прагмалигвистический подход анализирует цель анекдота и то, как он воспринимается аудиторией, принимая во внимание социальные и контекстуальные аспекты языка.*

Ключевые слова: *анекдоты, прагмалигвистический подход, перевод, языковые игры, межкультурные различия, социальный контекст, юмор, ирония, культурные намеки.*

Introduction.

Anecdotes, as a unique and distinctive genre of oral folk art, are an important means of expressing attitudes toward social life and evoking laughter. Anecdotes are not only a means of humor and jest but also reflect cultural and social norms. Anecdotes in different languages and cultures have unique characteristics, and translating them presents numerous challenges. The pragmalinguistic approach helps find effective ways to translate anecdotes by focusing on the pragmatic and contextual aspects of language. Anecdotes represent a unique and distinctive

genre of oral folk art, primarily used as a means of expressing attitudes toward social life and evoking laughter. Anecdotes have unique characteristics in different languages and cultures, and translating them presents numerous challenges. To translate anecdotes correctly and effectively, it is necessary to apply a pragmalinguistic approach. Pragmalinguistics studies how information can be conveyed accurately and effectively through language, focusing on the social and contextual aspects of language. This article analyzes the importance of anecdote translation and the pragmalinguistic approach.

Tarasenko's work "Anecdote and Translation (Using Language Games as an Example)" provides an in-depth analysis of the relationship between anecdote translation and language games. The research demonstrates the specific importance of language games in translating anecdotes, as anecdotes are often constructed through wordplay, irony, and cultural references. Tarasenko emphasizes the necessity of a pragmalinguistic approach in the process of anecdote translation because an anecdote reflects not only the grammatical structure of the language but also its pragmatic and contextual meaning. The research shows that anecdote translation should be carried out taking into account the social context of the language, cultural factors, and audience behavior.[1] The analysis conducted by Tarasenko proves the necessity of considering cross-cultural differences and disparities between them when translating anecdotes and language games. The research demonstrates that the pragmalinguistic approach allows for a deep analysis of semantic, stylistic, and pragmatic aspects in the process of anecdote translation.

Koller's work "Einführung in die Übersetzungswissenschaft" is considered an important scientific source as an introduction to translation science. This work illuminates the basic principles, theories, and practical approaches of the translation process. Koller analyzes the main approaches and methodologies used in translation science and separately examines the semantic, pragmatic, and stylistic aspects of translation. The work emphasizes the necessity of taking into account cross-cultural differences, relationships between languages, and communicative factors in translation.[2] By studying the development of translation theory, Koller provides an in-depth analysis of important components of translation science. Issues such as evaluating translation quality, cross-cultural differences in translation, and the role of language games occupy an important place in Koller's work. This scientific work serves as a useful source for specialists interested in studying the specific characteristics of translation science.

Bessonov's work "Blonde as a Character in Modern Anecdotes" analyzes the image of the blonde in the context of modern anecdotes. In the research, Bessonov shows how the image of the blonde is formed and developed in anecdotes and modern folklore. He analyzes how the portrayal of the blonde is expressed not only through wordplay and humor but also based on social stereotypes. The research examines how the blonde image is reflected in anecdotes as a strict, specific type and its cultural, linguistic, and pragmatic aspects.[3] Bessonov analyzes the specific characteristics of the blonde image and how intercultural connections play a role in creating this image. This work is considered an important source in research on anecdotes and folklore because it provides deep insights into the connections between language and culture, stereotypes, and their role in anecdotes.

Khimik's work "Anecdote as a Specific Phenomenon of the Russian Language" studies the anecdote and its role and significance in Russian language culture. In the research, Khimik analyzes the anecdote not only as humor or a specific story but as a phenomenon expressing the cultural and social identification of the Russian people. He studies the communicative functions of anecdotes, their role in language and culture, as well as their connection with irony, stereotypes, and other pragmatic factors.[4] The research shows that anecdotes are also

significant as a reflection of relationships in society, psychological states, and social norms in language. Khimik analyzes the linguistic and pragmatic aspects of anecdotes, explaining how they are formed and developed in the cultural environment. The research also pays special attention to the role of anecdotes in transmitting information in society, expressing emotional states, and fighting against social stereotypes. This work is considered an important scientific source for analyzing anecdotes, particularly in identifying their role and characteristics in Russian culture. Karasik's work "Comic Texts in Building Algorithms" analyzes the processes of creating comic texts and studies their structures and pragmatic aspects. In the research, Karasik identifies how comic texts are formed from a linguistic perspective, their communicative functions, and their impact on the audience. The work emphasizes the necessity of considering language, culture, and social factors in the construction and creation of comic texts. Karasik demonstrates changes in communication through comic texts, as well as the linguistic and pragmatic characteristics of humor.[5] He studies the basic algorithms in the process of creating comic texts and how they can be used to make the audience laugh or arouse interest. This work serves as an important scientific source for analyzing anecdotes and comic texts, placing great importance on linguistic and pragmatic aspects, and studying the role and characteristics of comic texts in linguistics.

Fix's work "Stand und Entwicklungstendenzen der Textlinguistik (I)" examines the current state and development trends in the field of text linguistics. In the research, Fix analyzes the basic concepts, methodology, and theoretical approaches of text linguistics. She studies the structure and functions of text, showing its importance in linguistics.[6] The work discusses the communicative aspects of text, its structural principles, and factors that shape language. Fix illuminates developments in the field of text linguistics, showing how it can be applied in text analysis and translation practice. Text linguistics is important in studying language, and advanced trends and scientific views in this field offer new methods for analyzing texts. This work serves as a useful source for scientists conducting research in the field of text linguistics. The translation of anecdotes depends on many factors, and in correctly transforming them, one must take into account the interconnection between language, culture, psychology, and social factors. Anecdotes include not only the grammatical features of language but also their pragmatic functions. In the pragmalinguistic approach, the purpose of language and the social context that arises during its use are of great importance. Through this approach, the original meaning of the anecdote and its reception by the audience are studied.

The main difficulty in translating words, phrases, and constructions used in anecdotes is related to cultural differences. Each language is distinguished by its cultural and social characteristics, so to fully and accurately translate a anecdote from one language to another, it is necessary to take into account social perception, pragmatic specifics of the language, and cultural sensitivity. The pragmalinguistic approach takes into account not only the meaning layers of language but also its contextual and pragmatic layers. When a translator is translating a anecdote into another language, they need to understand not only the correct translation of the word but also its contextual and pragmatic meaning. For example, when studying a anecdote like This man must be killed! this phrase is not limited to the words that exist only in writing, but how it is perceived by the audience and how they understand it is also important. Therefore, anecdote translation requires a pragmalinguistic approach because each anecdote has its specific purpose, often serving to express humor or irony, imagination, or a specific social opinion.

Applying a contextual approach complicates the process of anecdote translation. In translating anecdotes, ensuring grammatical correspondence is not enough. The translator should

not limit themselves to the correct translation of words but should also take into account the pragmatic and semantic layers of translating the original anecdote. A anecdote is often based on humor or wordplay, which makes its translation difficult. Therefore, in anecdote translation, the pragmalinguistic approach includes not only the grammatical structure of words but also the meaning and social context attached to them. If a anecdote is successful in one culture, it may not have the same effect in another culture. For example, a word that is perceived as funny or humorous in one culture may cause discomfort or anger in another culture. Thus, anecdote translation requires taking into account not only the language itself but also the differences between different cultures. A translator must deeply understand the specific characteristics of each culture to translate a anecdote correctly and sincerely.

Applying a pragmalinguistic approach in anecdote translation also helps to understand the interrelations of language, the pragmatic force of words, and layers of meaning. Each anecdote is developed with its social purpose in mind. A anecdote originally reflects not only wordplay and humor but also social norms, social level, and relationships between people. Therefore, applying a pragmalinguistic approach in transferring anecdotes to another language ensures high quality of translation. The pragmalinguistic approach in the process of anecdote translation takes into account not only language and culture but also the social functions of language. When a translator translates a anecdote from Uzbek to English, or vice versa, through anecdote translation, they must analyze the social context of the language, cultural codes, and audience behavior. This process ensures perfection in translation and preserves the cultural characteristics of the language. The basic principle of the pragmalinguistic approach in anecdote translation is viewing language as an interconnected and multi-layered system. A anecdote should not only be correctly translated linguistically, but its meaning, function, and reception by the audience should also be taken into account. Translators should consider not only linguistic knowledge but also cultural and social facts when translating anecdotes. For this, translators need to try to understand the multi-layered and multi-functional nature of each anecdote.

Applying a pragmalinguistic approach for the successful implementation of anecdote translation not only improves the quality of translation but also makes cross-cultural communication more effective. This approach ensures high efficiency in transferring anecdotes to another language and maximizes linguistic possibilities, taking into account cultural differences. In this way, the pragmalinguistic approach is considered one of the most important tools for effective and impactful anecdote translation.

Conclusion: In translating anecdotes, ensuring grammatical correspondence alone is not enough. It is necessary to take into account their social, pragmatic, and cultural aspects. Through the pragmalinguistic approach, the translator correctly analyzes the original meaning of the anecdote, how it is perceived by the audience, as well as cross-cultural differences. In the process of anecdote translation, it is important to take into account the specific characteristics of language and culture, identify its specific humor and irony elements, and the reactions of the audience. The analyses presented in the article demonstrate the importance of the pragmalinguistic approach in translating anecdotes and offer new directions for research in this field.

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